

Enhancing Quality in Childcare Centres through eQIAS: A Quasi-Experimental Study in Malaysian ECCE Settings

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ABSTRACT: This study evaluated the effectiveness of the electronic-Quality Improvement and Accreditation System (eQIAS) in enhancing the quality management practices of Early Childhood Care and Education Centres (ECCE) in Malaysia. Inspired by the QIAS model from Australia, eQIAS has been adapted to suit the Malaysian context, encompassing seven key quality dimensions. A quasi-experimental design using pre-test and post-test assessments was applied to 44 participants. Statistical analysis revealed consistent improvements across most quality dimensions following the implementation of eQIAS. Significant improvements were observed in Staff-child and interpersonal relationships, with mean scores increasing from 3.52 to 3.77 ($p = 0.001$), Children's learning and experiences from 3.51 to 3.70 ($p = 0.005$), and Health, nutrition, and well-being from 3.60 to 3.77 ($p = 0.022$). Marginal improvements were seen in Family partnerships (3.43 to 3.58, $p = 0.056$) and Programming and evaluation (3.55 to 3.67, $p = 0.072$). Although Safety and protection (3.70 to 3.77, $p = 0.272$) and Management that supports quality (3.38 to 3.53, $p = 0.103$) showed slight increases, these were not statistically significant. These findings affirmed the potential of eQIAS as a practical and effective tool for monitoring, assessment, and quality enhancement in early childhood centres. The integration of eQIAS contributes not only to raising the standard of care and education but also supports the national agenda in institutionalizing continuous quality improvement and accreditation across ECCE settings in Malaysia.

Key words: Quality Improvements and Accreditation System (QIAS), early childhood education, quality assurance, quality dimensions.

[Introduction](#)

[Literature review](#)

[Methodology](#)

[Findings and Discussion](#)

[Conclusion and Recommendations](#)

[References](#)

1. Introduction

Quality assurance in early childhood education plays a vital role in ensuring the development, safety, and holistic well-being of young children. A comprehensive and structured system is essential to provide a nurturing and enriching environment that supports both cognitive and socio-emotional growth. High-quality standards in early

childhood education contribute to lifelong learning, equity in education, and overall societal development.

In the context of childcare centers, quality becomes even more critical as these institutions directly shape the formative years of children. High-quality childcare centers emphasize trained caregivers, age-appropriate and engaging curricula, safe and clean facilities, and inclusive practices. These centers focus on nurturing a child's physical, emotional, social, and intellectual growth while ensuring their safety and well-being.

However, challenges in childcare centers are not uncommon. Issues such as unregistered childcare facilities, insufficiently trained caregivers, inadequate infrastructure, and lack of adherence to established standards can compromise the quality of care. These problems can hinder the development of children and raise concerns about their safety and holistic well-being.

To address these challenges, Malaysia has drawn inspiration from the internationally recognized Australian Quality Improvement and Accreditation System (QIAS) (Siti Noor, 2022, Hearn & Hildebrand, 2003; Harrison, 2008). The QIAS provides a robust framework for evaluating and improving the quality of early childhood programs. Acknowledging the cultural and contextual differences, Malaysia has adapted the QIAS into a localized model known as eQIAS. This model seeks to ensure that childcare centers in the country meet appropriate standards while being mindful of local needs and circumstances. By leveraging a structured and comprehensive framework like eQIAS, researcher aims to elevate the overall quality of early childhood education, ensuring the best outcomes for Malaysian youngest citizens.

eQIAS is a digital tool developed to support the national quality improvement agenda for early childhood education. It is structured around seven dimensions:

- (i) Staff-child and interpersonal relationships
- (ii) Family partnerships
- (iii) Programming and evaluation
- (iv) Children's learning and experiences
- (v) Safety and protection
- (vi) Health, nutrition, and well-being
- (vii) Management that supports quality

The eQIAS system is designed not only to serve as an internal improvement guide but also to provide external oversight for ensuring compliance with national childcare regulations.

2. Literature Review

The global discourse on early childhood education emphasizes the importance of structured quality frameworks to ensure holistic development in children. According to Siraj-Blatchford and Sylva (2004), high-quality early childhood settings are characterized by strong pedagogical leadership, professional development, and well-defined curricular goals. These aspects are often guided by quality assurance systems such as Australia's QIAS, which became a benchmark for several countries striving to improve their early childhood education (ECE) quality.

In Malaysia, the demand for quality childcare has increased in tandem with socio-economic developments and the participation of women in the workforce (Nor & Shahril, 2020). However, concerns regarding safety, unregistered centres, and under qualified staff have triggered the need for a unified quality monitoring system (Sulaiman et al., 2019). The adaptation of QIAS into eQIAS is in line with Malaysia's Education Blueprint for early childhood care and education, which stresses on assessment, accreditation, and continuous quality improvement.

Recent studies highlight the role of digital systems in streamlining data collection, performance tracking, and informed decision-making within ECE (UNESCO, 2021). Systems like eQIAS serve not only as assessment tools but also as catalysts for systemic change through the provision of real-time feedback and evidence-based practice support. As noted by Omar et al. (2023), digitalization in early education allows stakeholders to identify gaps and allocate resources more effectively.

Furthermore, the integration of Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics (STEAM) education in early childhood settings has been recognized as a means to foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Ng (2024) emphasizes the importance of empowering Malaysian early childhood practitioners through sustainable and inclusive practices in STEAM education. This approach not only enhances the quality of education but also prepares children for future challenges in a rapidly evolving technological landscape.

The World Bank (2024) underscores the necessity of improving early education to enhance skills in Malaysia, advocating for high-quality preschool education accessible to all children. This aligns with the objectives of eQIAS in ensuring equitable access to quality early childhood education.

Total Quality Management (TQM) in Childcare Centers

Total Quality Management (TQM) provides a structured approach to improving quality in childcare centers, focusing on continuous improvement, customer satisfaction, and employee involvement. Originally developed by quality pioneers such as W. Edwards Deming and Joseph Juran, TQM emphasizes creating a shared culture of quality where every stakeholder, including managers, caregivers, and families, contributes to excellence.

Key Principles of TQM in the Context of Childcare Centers:

1. **Customer Focus:** In childcare centers, the primary "customers" are children and their families. According to Acosta Jimenez (2023), applying TQM principles ensures that the developmental needs of children—including safety, emotional well-being, and holistic growth—are prioritized. Additionally, strong communication with families fosters trust and satisfaction, as highlighted in the OECD (2022) report on quality assurance in early education.

2. **Continuous Improvement:** Childcare centers implementing TQM emphasize regular assessment and enhancement of services. For example, Hanafi (2015) discusses the need for continuous refinement of curricula, caregiver training, and facilities to maintain relevance and effectiveness. Research by Sulaiman & Ng (2021) further supports this, highlighting how continuous improvement processes enhance employee competencies and childcare practices.

3. **Employee Empowerment:** Empowering caregivers and staff through active participation in decision-making fosters a sense of ownership and commitment. Acosta Jimenez (2023) examines how staff involvement leads to improved morale and retention rates, directly influencing service quality.

4. **Process Management:** Efficient management of childcare center operations is pivotal. As Juran (1989) emphasizes, process management streamlines daily routines, enrollment systems, and communication protocols to ensure consistent quality delivery.

There are 3 main aspects to consider when applying TQM to Childcare Centers. The first is in terms of Training and Development where according to Sulaiman & Ng (2021), caregivers should undergo regular professional development to stay aligned with emerging best practices in early childhood education. The second aspect is incorporating feedback mechanisms such as parent surveys and staff reviews which will allow centers to identify areas for improvement. Acosta Jimenez (2023) highlights the importance of these systems for adapting to dynamic needs. The third aspect is the benchmarking practice such as comparing childcare practices with high-performing centers to ensure adherence to quality standards. As suggested by the OECD (2022), benchmarking helps centres remain competitive and maintain excellence.

Applying TQM to childcare centres has its own benefits such as it will improve child development. This is stated by OECD (2022) that high-quality care fosters optimal growth in children's cognitive, social, and emotional dimensions. In addition, it will enhance parental trust and satisfaction. Hanafi (2015) claimed that families are more confident in centres that prioritize the safety and well-being of their children. TQM application in childcare centres also endorses higher staff retention and morale. This is mentioned by Acosta Jimenez (2023) that empowered caregivers demonstrate greater job satisfaction, reducing turnover and ensuring stable relationships with children. As a final point, TQM helps to elevate childcare quality because TQM is particularly relevant in addressing common challenges, such as unregistered childcare facilities, inconsistent standards, and untrained caregivers. By fostering accountability, continuous improvement, and stakeholder involvement, TQM serves as a robust framework for sustaining high-quality care. Research by Sulaiman & Ng

(2021) underscores the transformative potential of TQM in bridging gaps in quality assurance across childcare centres.

3. Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test design to evaluate the effectiveness of the eQIAS application. A total of 44 participants consisting of childcare centre operators and early childhood educators were selected for the study. All 44 respondents were randomly selected in each of the states involved, namely in Kedah, Penang and Selangor. Each participant was assessed using a structured instrument derived from the seven core dimensions of eQIAS. The assessment was conducted before and after a period of using the eQIAS application. Statistical analysis was performed using paired sample t-tests to determine the level of significance of improvements across dimensions.

The reliability of the instrument was previously verified through expert validation and inter-rater reliability testing (Siti Noor et.al. 2021), ensuring that the measurement tools reflected face, content, and construct validity.

4. Findings and Discussion

The data revealed that the implementation of the eQIAS application resulted in consistent improvements across most dimensions. The table below illustrates the comparative mean scores for each dimension before and after implementation:

Dimension	Pre-Test Mean	Post-Test Mean	Mean Difference	p-value	Significance
BK1: Staff-child and interpersonal relationships	3.5182	3.7677	+0.25	0.001	Significant
BK2: Family partnerships	3.4318	3.5795	+0.15	0.056	Marginal
BK3: Programming and evaluation	3.5455	3.6742	+0.13	0.072	Marginal
BK4: Children's learning and experiences	3.5083	3.7025	+0.19	0.005	Significant
BK5: Safety and protection	3.7045	3.7652	+0.06	0.272	Not Significant
BK6: Health, nutrition, and well-being	3.5974	3.7662	+0.17	0.022	Significant
BK7: Management that supports quality	3.3818	3.5273	+0.15	0.103	Not Significant

These findings can also be exhibited in a more interesting form as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores Across eQIAS Dimensions

The overall improvement in post-test scores indicates that eQIAS effectively supports quality enhancement in ECCE. The most substantial improvement occurred in Dimension BK1 (staff-child and interpersonal relationships), suggesting that eQIAS's reflective practice tools and monitoring features are particularly impactful in guiding interactional quality.

Significant gains in children's learning experiences (BK4) and health and well-being (BK6) dimensions suggest that the app promotes not only administrative monitoring but also direct pedagogical and caregiving improvements. Although family engagement (BK2) and programming (BK3) showed marginal improvements, they highlight areas that may benefit from more targeted training and practice support. The minimal change observed in safety and protection (BK5) may be attributed to an already high baseline performance, whereas management support (BK7) may require structural changes beyond what eQIAS alone can facilitate. While the improvements in family partnerships and programming (BK2 and BK3) were not statistically significant, they still demonstrate positive momentum. These areas may require supplementary interventions or policy support to sustain gains and deepen engagement.

eQIAS also adds value through its geo-tagging feature and central monitoring system, enabling authorities to detect unregistered centres, enhance compliance monitoring, and support data-driven policymaking. Furthermore, the consistent improvement across most dimensions supports the theoretical underpinnings of continuous quality improvement (CQI) models in early education. By embedding ongoing assessment, feedback loops, and structured reflection into daily practices, eQIAS enables educators to make evidence-based decisions that enhance the developmental outcomes of children. The use of digital technology to systematize these processes is especially critical in Malaysia, where disparities in service quality still persist.

Moreover, the eQIAS platform supports professional learning by exposing educators to best practices, creating a digital culture of quality, and encouraging data-driven conversations. It also strengthens institutional accountability by generating accessible reports that allow ECCE operators and policy-makers to monitor trends and prioritize areas for strategic investment.

Nearly 91% of prospective teachers believe they are up to date on the core ideas and theories of their fields of study. This conclusion is significant because it demonstrates a commitment to maintaining knowledge and expertise in their respective fields.

Regarding the incorporation of real-world experiences into their teaching practices, a substantial proportion of prospective teachers, or 58.0%, reported being highly skilled at incorporating real-world situations into their subject areas. Even though the current percentage is a good result, there is still room for improvement. The integration of tangible examples and real-world applications can enhance students' understanding and engagement with the material.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study confirms the utility of the eQIAS system in improving early childhood education quality indicators in Malaysia. The integration of systematic assessment tools, coupled with real-time data reporting and actionable feedback, makes eQIAS a valuable asset for continuous quality improvement in ECCE.

In addition to its monitoring capabilities, eQIAS fosters a culture of reflection, promotes inclusivity, and strengthens alignment with national early childhood development priorities. Its implementation addresses critical issues such as unregistered centres, lack of professional standards, and inconsistency in service delivery. The system also empowers educators with timely information, which enhances planning, improves interaction quality, and encourages reflective practices.

To maximize the effectiveness of eQIAS (electronic Quality Improvement and Accreditation System) in improving early childhood education, several recommendations should be implemented. These measures aim to strengthen the system's reach, impact, and alignment with national objectives, ultimately ensuring higher standards in childcare centers across Malaysia.

Firstly, prioritizing a nationwide rollout of eQIAS across all registered and unregistered Early Childhood Care and Education Centres, ECCE is essential. This step will ensure that all childcare centers, regardless of their registration status, adhere to standardized quality benchmarks. By providing equal access to eQIAS, the initiative can address disparities in quality and safety standards, especially in underserved areas.

Embedding Continuous Professional Development (CPD) modules within the eQIAS platform is another crucial strategy. These modules will enable educators and center managers to continuously enhance their skills and stay updated with best practices. With an emphasis on topics like child development, curriculum design, and safety protocols, CPD

programs can elevate the overall competency of staff and promote a culture of lifelong learning within the childcare sector.

The integration of eQIAS data into broader policy frameworks by the Ministry of Education and other stakeholders is a vital step. By aligning eQIAS outcomes with national education goals, policymakers can leverage data-driven insights to shape initiatives that benefit early childhood development. This alignment ensures consistency in quality management practices across childcare centers and contributes to achieving Malaysia's broader educational objectives.

Furthermore, conducting comprehensive research to refine the eQIAS tool and evaluate its long-term impacts is necessary. Studies should assess how eQIAS influences child development outcomes, transforms childcare institutions, and builds community trust. The insights gained from such research can help policymakers and stakeholders make evidence-based improvements to the system, ensuring its sustainability and effectiveness.

Regular training and professional development for PPAK staff should also be emphasized. These initiatives will equip caregivers and administrators with the knowledge and skills required to meet the demands of a high-quality early childhood program. By fostering a well-trained workforce, childcare centers can provide a nurturing environment that supports children's growth and learning.

Lastly, integrating eQIAS into existing national accreditation and licensing frameworks is essential for streamlining quality assurance processes. This integration will create a cohesive system that aligns licensing requirements with quality standards, minimizing redundancies and ensuring that all childcare centers meet the prescribed benchmarks.

By implementing these recommendations, eQIAS can become a transformative tool for elevating the quality of early childhood education across Malaysia. These steps ensure that the system is accessible, sustainable, and aligned with the country's aspirations for its youngest generation.

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